

**FROM THE HISTORY OF SAMARKAND UNIVERSITET OF
VETERINARY MEDICINE, ANIMAL HUSBANDRY AND
BIOTECHNOLOGIES: HISTORY OF THE FIRST HALF OF THE XX
CENTURY**

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Annotation The article examines the history of the state of the instituti, its role in the development of agriculture. The main emphasis is on the importance of the instituti in the development of agriculture, its contribution to increasing the productivity and quality of crops, protecting the environment and animal health, as well as the development of modern technologies and mechanization in agriculture in Uzbekistan.

Key words: Samarkand Agricultural Instituti, agriculture, Samarkand State University of Veterinary Medicine, Livestock and Biotechnology agronomy, veterinary medicine, Uzbekistan.

Аннотация Статья рассматривает историю состояние института, его роль в развитии сельского хозяйства. Основной акцент делается на значимости института в развитии сельского хозяйства, его вкладе в повышение производительности и качества сельскохозяйственных культур, охране окружающей среды и здоровья животных, а также развитию современных технологий и механизации в сельском хозяйстве Узбекистана

Ключевые слова: Самаркандский сельскохозяйственный институт, сельское хозяйство, Самаркандский государственный университет ветеринарной медицины, животноводства и биотехнологии, агрономия, ветеринария, Узбекистан.

Annotatsiya Maqolada institutning tarixi, qishloq xo‘jaligini rivojlantirishdagi o‘rni ko‘rib chiqiladi. Asosiy e‘tibor institutning qishloq xo‘jaligini rivojlantirishdagi ahamiyati, ekinlar mahsuldorligi va sifatini oshirish, atrof-muhit va hayvonlar salomatligini muhofaza qilish, shuningdek, O‘zbekistonda qishloq xo‘jaligida zamonaviy texnologiyalar va mexanizatsiyani rivojlantirishga qo‘shayotgan hissasiga qaratiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Samarqand qishloq xo‘jaligi instituti, qishloq xo‘jaligi, Samarqand davlat veterinariya meditsinasi, chorvachilik va biotexnologiyalar universiteti, agronomiya, veterinariya, O‘zbekiston.

Introduction. Samarkand Agricultural Instituti (Samarkand State University of Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology) was founded in 1929. This educational institution is currently one of the largest, prestigious institutions of higher education in the field of agriculture in our Republic. The instituti's faculties train specialists in various specialties. Among them are qualified agronomists, agrochemists, specialists in crop production, horticulture, selective seed production, forestry, veterinarians, agricultural mechanization engineers, vocational training, agricultural processing technologists and farm managers.

Currently, Samarkand State University of Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology has a material and technical base that meets the requirements of the time. The Instituti has the most modern technical facilities that meet the requirements of the time, laboratories, educational buildings, classrooms equipped with computers. The instituti has a scientific and information resource centre with the necessary teaching aids and books, as well as a sports complex and a student building. An educational and experimental farm for conducting scientific and practical classes, a training ground, and a vivarium serve students to acquire knowledge.

Review. Based on the requirements of the period, the institution is developing educational, methodological and scientific-practical cooperation with universities in a number of foreign countries - the USA, England, the Netherlands, Germany, Poland, Russia, China, Egypt, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan and

others [1]. Research at the instituti is mainly aimed at sustainable development of agriculture, increasing livestock productivity, creating new high-yielding and early-ripening varieties of agricultural crops, increasing soil fertility, preserving and improving the cleanliness of the environment, protecting livestock from various diseases and their effective treatment with agricultural machinery, creating effective machine unit systems. In agriculture, based on new conditions, effective work is being carried out to develop and implement improved methods of economic mechanism in enterprises with various forms of ownership.

As we know, the Republic of Uzbekistan takes its place among the countries of the Union. Soon after joining the union formed at the beginning of the 20th century, at the end of the 20s, fundamental changes began to occur in agriculture, collective farms and state farms began to form.

To manage these farms and develop the industries, many management personnel and specialists were required. Taking into account the above, the government of the republic paid great attention to this issue, considering the training of personnel for the agricultural sectors to be one of the urgent tasks.

Analysis. On December 13, 1929, the government of Uzbekistan adopted a decree on the opening of preparatory courses at the Samarkand Cotton Instituti.

Agricultural educational institutions were created in a number of cities of our republic - Kokand, Bukhara, Karman, and the State Instituti of Cotton Growing and the State Veterinary Instituti of Uzbekistan were created in the city of Samarkand [2].

At that time, the Uzbek State Instituti of Cotton Growing included the faculties of cotton growing, mechanization, crop production and irrigation. Preparatory courses were organized for admission to higher education institutions. Classes on these courses began in 1929, and from this year the instituti began its activities.

In addition, during the same period, the Uzbek Higher Communist Agricultural School was created in Samarkand, training leaders for agriculture. The Uzbek State Agro-Commercial University also trained personnel for mid-level agriculture. Training

of specialists was also carried out in horticultural, veterinary, and irrigation technical schools.

Training classes at the Uzbek State Veterinary Instituti were held in the buildings of the Pedagogical Academy (now SamSU) and technical schools, and then in the building of the Central Savings Bank, which at that time was transferred to the instituti, where the Samarkand branch of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan is now located.

All educational institutions and student dormitories, despite their accessibility, caused great difficulties due to the lack of teachers to conduct classes according to the curriculum [3]. Despite this, these educational institutions with their personnel have made a worthy contribution to the development of all sectors of agriculture in Uzbekistan. It is not difficult to imagine under what difficult conditions these organized educational institutions began their activities.

The insufficiency of classrooms, equipment, material and technical base for the training of qualified personnel, as well as the insufficient preparedness of applicants and the lack of teachers for their training created great difficulties in the activities of the instituti. When hundreds of young people arrived from the villages, many of them were not yet ready to study. However, in those years, the republic urgently needed new-thinking personnel working in new conditions, with confidence and firmness [4]. Educational work was constantly being improved, although the material and technical base of the instituti was weak to continue educational and scientific work.

Due to the great importance of higher educational institutions in the development of the republic, this issue was under the constant control of the Chairman of the Council of People's Commissars of the Republic of Uzbekistan Fayzulla Khodjaev. That is why the directors often attended his reception on issues related to the activities of the instituti.

In the pre-war years, much attention was paid to the training of engineering and mechanical personnel for agriculture. There were not enough tractors and machinery in those years. That is why the American companies Inter, Caterpillar and Joinder provided us with great help by selling their cars [5]. By the end of the first five-year

plan, more than 90% of the land in our republic was plowed. Plowing the land with tractors was just a dream of our peasants. The instituti had a faculty of agronomy with the largest number of students, and agronomists played an important role in implementing agricultural policy in rural areas.

Results. In the mid-thirties, the Instituti's scientists achieved notable success in their work to promote production. In carrying out this work, students used their organizational skills and dedicated work. In production, agronomists and livestock specialists were the main specialists and became the decisive force.

Agronomists were among the first in the world to use new methods in agriculture to combat insects and diseases by applying mineral fertilizers, planting new varieties of cotton, and introducing modern agricultural technology. With the help of scientists from the veterinary faculty, in 1937 it was possible to get rid of pulmonary colds, plague, and equine tuberculosis in cattle. The incidence of anthrax in animals has sharply decreased [6].

From the first days of the war, many personnel and students went to the front to defend their homeland. Many died in battle, but bravely withstood the trials of such harsh days that befell them. The war required the reorganization of everything in the front-line areas. This concerned not only industrial, but also scientific and educational institutions. In Samarkand, all higher educational institutions were closed, except for the instituti. But the Samarkand Agricultural Instituti did not stop its activities for a day. Because in addition to steel, cast iron, and coal, the country also needed bread, cotton, meat, horticultural and vegetable products.

In November 1941, the Moscow Military Veterinary Academy was included in the instituti on the basis of the Moscow Agricultural Academy and the Veterinary Faculty named after K.A. Timiryazev (now the Moscow Veterinary Academy named after P.I. Scriabin). The instituti's staff created conditions for the evacuated scientists and shared everything with them. The studies were organized in three shifts in such a way as not to interrupt the educational process of the three higher educational institutions, using the material and technical base of the instituti in full. Hundreds of

arrivals were accommodated in the apartments of instituti employees and other houses [7]. To organize classes in classrooms and laboratories, special schedules began to be drawn up. In such difficult conditions, there were no interruptions in the organization of lectures, laboratory, practical and scientific work in three educational institutions.

Employees and students of the Moscow Instituti of Leather and Fur constantly accessed the library of the instituti. They were located on the basis of the Research Instituti of Karakul Breeding. The Kharkov Agricultural Instituti, as well as the Krasnodar Instituti of Viticulture, Winemaking and Tobacco, and the Leningrad Film Instituti were evacuated to the city of Kattakurgan. Training at these institutis began between weeks after the arrival of food trains loaded with training equipment. Our scientists began to gain experience from educational, methodological, scientific work and combine scientific research with these scientists.

During the difficult recovery years, the instituti's staff faced great challenges. Of these, the renovation of existing educational buildings, dormitories, the construction of new buildings, the improvement of educational and methodological, scientific research, spiritual and educational work, development, etc. The teaching staff, graduate students-researchers conducted research experiments in the organizations organized at that time at the Instituti of educational and experimental farms (a rice plot behind Chapanata, a plot in Charkhin and a plot in Arabkhana), in large farms (former state and collective farms, livestock farms and collections) [8]. Cooperation was established with the scientists of this instituti in the scientific and methodological field of the teaching staff of the agricultural instituti; the scientific councils included members from both sides.

During these years, as a result of large-scale construction work, the instituti opened educational buildings, student dormitories, canteens, a student recreation area, and dispensaries. In order to improve the educational process, a training ground, educational farm, poultry farm, and greenhouses were built. The Faculty of Mechanization has opened courses for machinists, tractor drivers, and combine

harvesters. All students received an official driving record along with their major diploma. A sufficient amount of equipment was purchased to organize this process.

Conclusions. To summarize, it should be said that all opportunities for the development of the institution were aimed at:

Televisions and modern equipment were installed in all classrooms; special technical equipment was purchased at the instituti to ensure the educational process; a film and photo laboratory was opened.

In order to modernize the organization of the scientific and educational process, a special computer science department and a central scientific laboratory were created at the instituti.

In order to strengthen control and management of the educational process, a system for managing the training of special personnel was developed and implemented at the instituti; in a short time, an educational, methodological and material and technical base that met the requirements of the time was created at the new faculties.

REFERENCES

1. Salievich K. S. The paradigm challenge to reflexive sociology //Thematic Journal of Social Sciences. 2022. Т. 8. №. 2.
2. Сафаров А. И., Ризаев И. И. Роль исторического сознания и исторической памяти в системе национального сознания //Культурное наследие и народное искусство: сохранение и актуализация в целях устойчивого развития общества. – 2022. С. 297-303.
3. Alikulov X., Haqqulov N. Q. Spiritual maturity and philosophical thinking dependence of development //ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science. 2020. Т. 4. №. 84. С. 164-167.
4. “Samarqand qishloq xo‘jaligi instituti 70 yoshda” Samarqand-1999. С-5-7.
5. Ризаев И. И., Муминова З. О. Профессиональная подготовка личности: оздоровление и духовное воспитание //Система менеджмента качества в вузе: здоровье, образованность, конкурентоспособность. 2021. С. 264-

6. Саматов Х. У. Парадигмальная сущность социально-экономической системы Узбекистана //Парадигма современной науки в условиях модернизации и инновационного развития научной мысли: теория и практика. – 2022. – С. 406-408.
7. Khotambekovna E. M. Таълимда инновацион ғоялар кириб келишидаги хаотик жараёнлар ҳамда таълим тизимида аттрактор омили //Philosophy and life international journal. – 2022. – №. SI-1.
8. Усмонов Ф. Н. Основные этапы развития научной рациональности //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2017. – №. 11. – С. 181-184.
9. Кубаева Ш. Т. Развитие инновационного мышления в Самаркандской академии Улугбека //Universum: общественные науки. – 2014. – №. 5 (6).С. 2.
10. Мардонов Р. С., Ризаев И. И. Проблемы в инновационном развитии (на примере Узбекистана) //Географические и экономические исследования в контексте устойчивого развития государства и региона. – 2022. – С. 244-246.
11. Muminova Z. O. Spiritual moral beying of humans in the sinergetik context //Austrian journal of humanities and social sciences. – 2015. – Т. 3.
12. Тураев Б. О., Ризаев И. И. Особенности проявления искусственного интеллекта в бытии человека //Новые информационные технологии и системы (НИТиС-2022). – 2022. – С. 361-363.
13. Mamarahimov K. The need to improve the process of developing aesthetic knowledge and skills in youth at a new stage of development //American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development. – 2022. – Т. 11. – С. 45-49.
14. Mardonov R. Features of educational services in modern conditions //Archive of Conferences. – 2021. – Т. 22. – №. 1. – С. 100